

CONCEPTS OF FORMING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This article presents concepts and theoretical analyzes of the management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises. In addition, the relevance of conceptual, theoretical and practical researches and innovative processes, views on the management of scientific and technical development depends on many reasons.

The concepts of the market were often raised to an absolute level, while not taking into account a certain convention of theoretical models, their abstraction from specific conditions, flexible restrictions, which had a negative impact on the practical results of the work of industrial enterprises.

First, the study of scientific and technical aspects of economic development is becoming more and more important and is demanded by the economy. Theory and economic practice, it is related to their impact on the dynamics of economic parameters, level of quality of life, competitiveness, economic security.

Secondly, a methodological understanding of the problems and tasks of managing the growth of the innovative economy, in particular, the industrial-industrial complex, is necessary to form a theoretical basis for making clear management decisions to determine the directions and structure of the innovative economy. development of the economic complex, innovative development and modernization models, as well as the selection of methods and tools, management systems of the scientific and technological revolution.

Thirdly, the rapid pace of economic changes in Russia led to the implementation of a number of theoretical rules.

Fourth, as shown by the development dynamics of the world economy and noted in the researches of many scientists, high-tech production is not only a strengthening of competitiveness, but also a decisive factor. A condition for the survival, economic and political stability of society. The theoretical basis of modern concepts of management of scientific and technical development is based on the heritage of economic thought - scientific views and rules, ideas and paradigms. Research and understanding of the role and essence of management in economic systems with different levels of development of productive forces and production relations in different historical periods. The unifying component of these views is the almost universally recognized importance of scientific and technical progress and

its impact. State and dynamics of the economic system. However, in general, opinions on the selection of tools, forms and methods of the innovation management system, in particular, on the determination of conditions and time for scientific and technical development, as well as technological stagnation, often differ. The need to analyze concepts and methodological views on the content, mechanisms and means of managing science and technology development is connected with several reasons. The most important are: The need to analyze concepts and methodological views on mechanisms and tools is connected with several reasons. The most important are: The need to analyze concepts and methodological views on mechanisms and tools is connected with several reasons. The most important are:

- the existence of different, often contradictory views on;
- management of innovations and scientific and technical development;
- that a number of theoretical concepts are not connected with reality;
- dynamics of economic processes, specific historical and economic conditions;
- the importance of a theoretical platform for making management decisions;
- the scale of losses or successes of the economy determined by the results of management of scientific and technical progress;
- the error in determining the priorities of management affects the formation of theoretical rules and practical management.

In order to systematize the conceptual and theoretical foundations of the management of science and technology development, it is necessary to understand how views on the importance and functional content of management activities have changed, and how the assessment of the importance of management activities has changed. Formed the priority tasks of management of factors and scientific and technical development. The opinions of scientists on the management of economic relations, scientific and technical development are summarized, and it is necessary to analyze them retrospectively, because the root of many misconceptions in the formation of the theoretical basis and practical solutions in the management of scientific and technical development is wrong. ri conclusions arise from incorrect analogies of theoretical heritage. Theory and concepts are evaluated based on the proposed systematization. Views on the role of market factors and state influence on the dynamics of scientific and technical development. The influence of state power on economic processes was noted by mercantilists.

At the end of the 16th - beginning of the 17th century, serious changes in the economy were associated with the growth of industrial production, industrialization, and the development of market mechanisms. During this period, supporters of the classical school (classical economics) formulated the ideas of economic liberalism, among which they proposed minimizing the influence of the state on economic processes. Proving the need for the state to refrain from interfering in economic life, justifying the efficiency of self-regulation of the market through the mechanism of competition, the proponents of classical economics recognized the need for such intervention, for example, from the point of view of taxation.

The classical school, which has been the basis for many of the most modern economic theories, not only recognizes the necessity of certain rules (4 rules of taxation by A. Smith), but actually proves that they cannot be established without their participation. state. Later, neoclassical economics agreed with the most important postulates of the classical theory and

focused on the inevitable need for the state to intervene in the economy, because economic freedoms create conditions for efficient production, but do not ensure a fair distribution of economic benefits. In the 1930s and 1940s, the emergence of the Keynesian approach to the study of many management aspects of the scientific and technological revolution. The last century was prepared by objectively implemented socio-economic changes: as a result of the increase in the scale of production and competition, the integration of economic structures, the influence of new factors of economic development, including scientific and technological influences. there were changes in the system of market relations. The consequence of these processes is that, according to the difficulty, the influence of the state can be decisive in certain periods of development without weakening the efficiency of market mechanisms. In modern theory and practice, the terms are used more and more - "Post-industrial society", "information society", "knowledge economy" are considered in the works of D. Bell, E. Toffler, K. Drogobitskaya and a number of other scientists. However, some terminological restrictions do not always reflect the essence of the views. Scientists do not deny the role and growth of the impact of production processes on the economy, but they emphasize the scientific and informational factors of development, including industrial development, and emphasize that the effectiveness of the latter depends more and more on development. knowledge Agreeing with a number of conclusions made by the representatives of the post-industrial development paradigm, it should be noted that it is theoretical. For example, the conclusions studied for economically backward countries are not significant. they emphasize that. knowledge Agreeing with a number of conclusions made by the representatives of the post-industrial development paradigm, it should be noted that it is theoretical. For example, the conclusions studied for economically backward countries are not significant. they emphasize that. knowledge Agreeing with a number of conclusions made by the representatives of the post-industrial development paradigm, it should be noted that it is theoretical. For example, the conclusions studied for economically backward countries are not significant.

Their obvious declarativeness is understandable, at least due to the lack of macroeconomic proposals, mechanisms and ways to transform them into countries with a rapidly developing, independent, competitive economy. The decisive impact of scientific and technical progress, the increasing role of technocracy in the development of the economy, led to a qualitatively new understanding of the ongoing processes and their management, which supporters of the institutional theory were among the first to pay attention to. So in TB's case. Veblen's "Leisure Class Theory" provides an objective assessment of the theoretical, often detached from life, models of the neoclassics. Monetarists M. Friedman, F. Hayek and other scholars follow different views about the role of the government. When studying the problems of economics and management efficiency, they focus only on the financial sector, whose role has undoubtedly increased many times since the mid-1970s. of the last century. All other areas of activity remained outside the scope of serious research by monetarists and their supporters. The limitation of these views and theoretical concepts, we believe, lies primarily in the silence or denial of their role by monetarists, either intentionally or through misunderstanding. All other areas of activity remained outside the scope of serious research by monetarists and their supporters. The limitation of these views and theoretical concepts, we believe, lies primarily in the silence or denial of their role by monetarists, either

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Industry, traditional industry is the production that is the basis of economic development.

Undoubtedly, the structure of industrial production and even its content is changing significantly in the context of the emergence and development of new information and communication technologies, not only computerization of production, but also the design of production management systems characteristic of the modern technological structure. The most important criterion of efficiency is the increase in the volume of production, labor productivity is provided by the lower number of workers in the production sector. In our opinion, D. Bell's opinion that there is no substitute for industrial production in the information society is true. Production will receive a new one. Content and structural aspects necessary for social development. Practice proves the correctness of the conclusions made by D. Bell. The industrial potential of the most economically developed countries did not decrease with the transition to a new technological system and the emergence of radically new phenomena and processes in the technological and information sphere, but the number of people engaged in scientific research increased. and development. Labor resources released as a result of high-quality new technologies logically enter the field of scientific research, technological development, services, including information services, and ensure their development and improvement. In developed countries, the management of these complex processes has become the most important state function, because the competitiveness and independence of the national economy largely depends on them.

The main idea of his research is to revise the models of economic growth, which he believes to be the basis of technological progress. J. Schumpeter proved the interdependence of production-technological and economic relations and emphasized that technology itself (more precisely, this term is used by him to express technical and technological aspects in the broadest sense of this concept) is impossible without the influence of effective management levers. provides high productivity. He also takes the first place in confirming the priority of the impact of technological progress on the growth of profits. J. Schumpeter's ideas were supported by many scientists. So, G. Mensch in the 70s. The economic growth trends of the 20th century, first of all, the main, defined the idea that technological innovations and leaps in the economy are determined by their high concentration. In our opinion, G. Mensch's hypothesis is that the company's condition worsens, depression can be seen as a stimulus to push technology. There are significant differences in the evaluation of strategic alternatives for economic development. Thus, M. Porter considered technological innovation as the basis of the success of the cost leadership strategy, and product innovation as the basis of the success of the differentiation strategy. G. Mensch., Yu. Yakovets, M. Dvortsin, V. Yusim, the main factor of the efficiency of the entire economy, the success of the enterprise development strategy and the growth of its profit are rightly considered to be technological innovations. N. Kondratiev, J. Schumpeter, K. Peres, Y. Yakovets, S. Glazyev in the theories of economic development with all the differences - detailing different levels of research, periodicization of

economic cycles, different emphasis - innovative technological processes. considered as the basis of economic growth. Nobel laureate R. Solow also considers new technologies to be the most important factor of economic growth. Analyzing the reasons for the rapid growth of labor productivity in the United States (it doubled from 1909 to 1949), the economist concludes about the main role of technological change and innovation (the contribution of innovation is $7/8$, and capital is $7/8$). growth is only $1/8$ of the total productivity growth). P. Drucker, a well-known expert in the field of management theory, also studied economics, especially notes the crucial importance of technological progress and increasing labor productivity for developing countries. According to him, protectionist measures became the first defensive reaction against external competitors. His assessment of the problems faced by innovative active organizations is of great importance.

While studying innovation risks, P. Drucker identified three main "traps" (Three Traps) that such an enterprise can fall into:

1. The product of scientific and technical development should be consistent with the main strategy of the company. It must also respond to economic, demographic and political realities.

2. The second pitfall is related to the exchange of concepts. Often, an innovation is an upgrade to an existing product or service. This phenomenon often occurs when the management of the enterprise wants to get out of the regular production cycle, but for one reason or another is not ready for real scientific and technological development.

3. The third trap is related to the need to make a decision to stop the production of goods, works, services that sooner or later stopped bringing income. However, if the management does not answer the questions of what happened in the market and how it should develop in the future, before making an important decision, there will be no fundamental changes in the enterprise. According to P. Drucker, each organization has its main competencies depending on the profile of the company. However, regardless of the profile, each organization should have competencies in the field of innovation development. An interesting enough, in our opinion, view of the scientific-technical paradigm to base the theoretical platform of the research was presented by K. Peres, a prominent representative of neo-Schumpeterism. In particular, it emphasizes that all interested market agents participate in the process of technological development: suppliers, distributors, consumers, etc. Due to the high level of mobility of the external environment, increased competition, the need to ensure competitive advantages and the main success factors for enterprises, manufactured products and the economy as a whole, the need for scientific and technical development of the economy is increasing. Achieving these complex goals, in turn, largely depends on the overall effect of factors formed at the macro and micro levels of management. This Due to the high level of mobility of the external environment, increased competition, the need to ensure competitive advantages and the main success factors for enterprises, manufactured products and the economy as a whole, the need for scientific and technical development of the economy is increasing. Achieving these complex goals, in turn, largely depends on the overall effect of factors formed at the macro and micro levels of management. This Due to the high level of mobility of the external environment, increased competition, the need to ensure competitive advantages and the main success factors for enterprises, manufactured products and the

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depression, recession. A number of researchers, for example, OS Sukharev, pay attention to the unevenness of innovative scientific and technological activity. K. Peres's ideas about the "revolutionary" nature of technological development can be seriously criticized, because it is very difficult to define "revolutionary" criteria, while in modern conditions evolutionary scientific-technical dynamics leads to completely revolutionary results. Based on his position, K. Peres concludes: the technical revolution is the main revolution in the production potential of the economy, which opens up wide innovation opportunities and creates a combination of the latest technologies, infrastructure and organizational principles, which significantly increases production efficiency. can increase. efficiency of all spheres of life. In support of the last part of his conclusions, we consider scientific and technical development as a phenomenon (in terms of results) and a process (in terms of dynamics), as well as management, rather than the technical revolution as the basis of growth. we go out this process is at different levels. Almost all researchers of the problems of innovative development of the economy emphasize the inefficiency of the current socio-economic processes and management system of scientific and technical development in Russia. Within the scope of this thesis, it is impossible to thoroughly analyze the concepts of economic development of the country and its most important part - scientific and technical development, proposed by scientists. However, two main related conceptual positions with different concepts and models can be distinguished. One of them was developed by a team of scientists led by L. Gohberg.

Ya. Kuzminova, V. Mau, and "Strategy-2020", and the position of the scientists of the Institute of Modern Development (INSOR) is added to it. According to the terminology proposed by S. Gubanov, another conceptual position with a certain degree of generalization is usually called neo-industrial. Despite the existing differences in seeing the problems and prospects of strategic innovative development, the views of scientists such as R. Grinberg, S. Gubanov, V. Ivanter, G. Fetisov, S. Glazyev have a common basis. S. Glazyev's scientific positions are largely consistent with the concept of neo-industrialization, so it seems possible to combine them into a common conceptual block. The first conceptual approach is that of institutionalists as well as monetarists. are based on their points, their important theoretical positions were formed by M. Friedman, F. Hayek. Strategy 2020 has undergone significant updates, in which some liberal proposals have been significantly polished. At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be

noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include: formulated by Hayek. Strategy 2020 has undergone significant updates, in which some liberal proposals have been significantly polished. At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include: formulated by Hayek. Strategy 2020 has undergone significant updates, in which some liberal proposals have been significantly polished. At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include: At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include: At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include: At the same time, in our opinion, the authors of this concept most clearly formulated the tasks, imperatives and goals of entering the innovative path of development of the Russian economy. It should be noted that in 2008, the national report "Innovative development - the basis of the modernization of the Russian economy" clearly defined two main factors that determined the development of the world economy in the last three decades. These include:

- innovative behavior of enterprises;
- innovation policy of the state.

In the assessment of macroeconomic processes, special attention is paid to "increasing the innovative component in the state's activities, changes in the mechanisms of support for science and innovation in each country" [67, p. 17]. When analyzing the current situation and determining the impact of innovative processes on the results of economic development, it can be said that the analyzed concepts are similar. It seems necessary to emphasize that it is in the first conceptual position.

The main means of state innovation policy and incentives: tax incentives, focus on energy-efficient technologies, directing state orders to innovative competitive products, as well as using advanced global experience in the field of IT technologies and education. True, in our opinion, experts say that the obvious side effect of funding science from the budget is the "retention of the Soviet model" in modern reality. In fact, for example, as a result of the analysis of internal financing of research and development costs, it was found that budget financing is more than 65% . This is higher than in most economically developed countries. However, it must be admitted that the proposed Strategy 2020 has not been implemented in practice, which, in turn, is also related to the fact that the authors did not pay serious

attention to the management aspects of innovative development. The conclusions of L. Gohberg and T. Kuznetsova about the need to create and support conditions for the development of strategic innovators, stimulate their activities, connect them with scientific centers and universities, but what mechanisms should be theoretical and even more practically justified. A lens is used to achieve these goals. , the authors do not suggest. Specialists and scientists gathered around the strategic concept, studied a lot of data, including statistical data, conducted serious comparative studies of the innovation potential of Russia and other countries, conducted predictive studies. After a long hiatus, they were the first to make long-term forecasts of socio-economic and scientific-technical development at the macroeconomic level. However, the generalization and isolation from real socio-economic processes, which are characteristic of many conceptual rules, are the cause of criticism of opponents.

All analysts and researchers recognize that Russia lags behind the economies of developed countries in terms of parameters of scientific and technical development, regardless of conceptual views. Most of them also recognize that the dynamics of the scientific and technical revolution is now becoming a decisive factor in the competitiveness of enterprises and countries. Thus, S. Glazyev describes the emerging sixth technological order (technological periodization is based on N. Kondratyev's theory of "long waves") proves the leading role of the technological component in innovative development, and also emphasizes its specific features. the sixth technological order, namely:

- high growth rates (up to 35% per year);
- the stability of the growth rate, which is not interrupted by the crisis or subsequent depression processes in the economy. Regarding the thesis research problem, the idea that innovative performance is determined by a system of long-term technological priorities is important in the first concept.

The representatives of the second approach prove that scientific and technical progress is a decisive condition for eliminating systemic economic backwardness and forming an effective competitive economy, and emphasize the neo-industrial paradigm based on the law of vertical integration. Its essence is "in the systematic interconnection of intermediate and final production, such an interdependence between them, in which the maximum rate of turnover of gross production capital at the expense of zero profitability in intermediate links is "rides".

In our opinion, supporters of these views recognize that the overcoming of stagnation, industrial achievement, the emergence of the Russian economy in the direction of growth depends "only on neo-industrialization, as a technotronic stage." ' is not always reliable in emphasis.

Industrialization and the process of formation of a production method requiring knowledge". This point of view is supported by Russian scientists V. Daskovskiy, R. Kuchukov, R. Grinberg, S. Tolkachev, as well as Belarusian scientists, among whom V. Bainev, V. Vinnik are the most consistent. The post- and neo-industrial stage of development is mainly characteristic of highly developed countries that have advanced technologies, long-term cheap financing and the possibility of locating production in developing countries (which solves some of the social problems of these countries, but does it). does not contribute to their

economic independence and the establishment of an innovative path of economic development). S. Gubanov emphasizes that the core of the economy of developed countries is made up of transnational corporations, which are based on vertically integrated relations, which mainly provide benefits in solving the problems of scientific and technical development. He states that in management "developed powers are close to state capitalism". When studying the problems of management of scientific and technical development, as a rule, separate levels or links of management are studied. Thus, A. Malyugin, V. Ilyin, A. Gubernatorov, I. Savelyev analyze the current problems of managing changes in innovative activity at the regional level. Macroeconomic aspects of management A. Amosov, A. Alekseev, N. Kuznetsov, A. Golubev, R. Kuchukov and many other scientists. N. Abdikeyev, A. Kiselev, N. Ivanova, M. Kamenskikh focus on tasks and problems of innovative development of corporations and enterprises. The importance of the cluster approach in the implementation of innovative development tasks is expressed in the works of E. Kutsenko, D. Tyumentsev. M. Dvortsin and his supporters made a significant contribution to the development of the theoretical foundations of the study of technological development, which was reflected in the works on technodynamics: in these, it is of fundamental importance The importance of the cluster approach in the implementation of innovative development tasks is expressed in the works of E. Kutsenko, D. Tyumentsev. M. Dvortsin and his supporters made a significant contribution to the development of the theoretical foundations of the study of technological development, which was reflected in the works on technodynamics: in these, it is of fundamental importance The importance of the cluster approach in the implementation of innovative development tasks is expressed in the works of E. Kutsenko, D. Tyumentsev. M. Dvortsin and his supporters made a significant contribution to the development of the theoretical foundations of the study of technological development, which was reflected in the works on technodynamics: in these, it is of fundamental importance research is the study of changes in technologies that determine the basis of "the creation of fundamentally new production systems representing the unity of education, production, science". He emphasizes that the organization of the process of scientific and technical development precedes economic income. However, the problems of adjusting the control system as a whole have not been studied in practice. It is known that planning, organization, regulation, motivation and control are the main general management functions in classical management. The study of different points of view, the summarization of theoretical and practical materials provides the basis for the following conclusions on the development of theoretical ideas about the development of science and technology:

- management creates conditions for technological development, ensures its dynamics;
- in modern conditions, management is becoming a strategic resource for the scientific and technical development of enterprises, industry and the entire economy;
- in the formation and development of the management system of scientific and technical development, it is necessary to take into account its dichotomous nature and the resulting features revealed in section 1.3 of this work.

Since socio-economic processes are characterized by dynamism, economic theories are developed and changed, basic economic laws and regularities not only apply, but also adapt to specific historical conditions, improve and develop, new ideas and doctrines appear. Claims

about the absolute truth and universality of theoretical studies completed in economics are not justified. The relativity of economic doctrines is recognized by most scientists and economists. Even a theory confirmed by practice is not universal and does not apply to any specific historical

conditions, in different countries, at different stages of economic development. In practice, the most reasonable choice is to choose such management decisions that are consistent with the principle of flexibility and are implemented on the basis of current theoretical developments, analytical research, taking into account the accumulated experience in the management of specific objects and processes. Thus, the theoretical basis underlying the socialist model of the economy does not at all mean that it cannot be used in some cases for the creative purposes of developing a new, efficient, innovation-oriented model. For example, the multi-factor productivity model developed by American scientists is widely used in China's economic management and scientific and technical development. but adapted to the conditions of this country and provides growth of the gross domestic product from 40 to 48 percent. Overcoming the slowdown in the growth rate of the Chinese economy is primarily related to the mastery and development of industrial production sectors, for example, household appliances, electronics (they already provide 10% of the country's export revenue), software production of supplies and smartphones. Customer-oriented innovation in industry, as well as the rapid development of science and technology, will be critical to the creation of high-value-added and high-wage jobs and thus to the success of Chinese industry. Overcoming the slowdown is primarily related to the development and adoption of industrial production sectors, such as household appliances, electronics (which already provide 10% of the country's export earnings), software and smartphones production. Customer-oriented innovation in industry, as well as the rapid development of science and technology, will be critical to the creation of high-value-added and high-wage jobs and thus to the success of Chinese industry. Overcoming the slowdown is primarily related to the development and adoption of industrial production sectors, such as household appliances, electronics (which already provide 10% of the country's export earnings), software and smartphones production. Customer-oriented innovation in industry, as well as the rapid development of science and technology, will be critical to the creation of high-value-added and high-wage jobs and thus to the success of Chinese industry. electronics (they already provide 10% of the country's export earnings), software and smartphone production. Customer-oriented innovation in industry, as well as the rapid development of science and technology, will be critical to the creation of high-value-added and high-wage jobs and thus to the success of Chinese industry. electronics (they already provide 10% of the country's export earnings), software and smartphone production. Customer-oriented innovation in industry, as well as the rapid development of science and technology, will be critical to the creation of high-value-added and high-wage jobs and thus to the success of Chinese industry.

For the Russian management, the theoretical understanding and study of the Chinese experience is of particular importance due to the geographical compatibility and the expansion of economic cooperation. Thus, the theoretical developments of foreign and Russian scientists, the experience of managing the scientific and technological development of different countries, adapted to specific historical and economic conditions, can be very

effectively used in the management of industry and industrial enterprises in Russia. However, to successfully solve problems a comprehensive approach is needed to generalize theoretical views and practical innovations in the scientific and technological sphere. 1.2 Clarifying the theoretical rules of managing the scientific and technical development of industrial enterprises. For a long time, the export-raw model of managing the economy was implemented in Russia, as a result of which the economic situation described by S. was created. Gubanov with the term "growth without progress" and after the crisis of 2008-2010. became a situation of "neither development nor growth". Mistakes in management have led to serious problems related to deindustrialization, education, personnel, significant loss of scientific and technical potential. Deformation processes, as well as the result of the ongoing scientific-technical and industrial policy, which did not help to restore the remaining potential, is the low level of scientific-technical development of the Russian economy, dependence on industry, including industrial imports. high-tech products, which, in turn, lead to the weakening of national security, cause problems of a social nature. Studies conducted on a wide range of indicators for several years show that the level of scientific and technical progress in Russia generally lags behind the level of economically developed countries, and the influence of management does not correspond to the complexity of tasks. if it has a level of innovative development, the dynamics of changes in scientific and technical processes will overcome the existing delay.

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